

Framing American Trade Policy: The Analysis of Ideological Representation in Trump's Discourse

Ph.D. Abbas Lutfi Hussein

drabslutfi@yahoo.com

Halah Qasim Mohammed

halaamohammed.82@gmail.com

Abstract

American Trade policy identified with different ideologies during Trump administration. The trade policy framing has changed with new ideologies toward the international trade system. Previous works have concentrated on Trump's trade strategies impacts across the international trade with no attention to the role of ideologies in framing these strategies. This study explores the framing of American Trade Policy during Trump's era (2017-2020) with the main ideological representation embedding in *United States Trade Representative* (USTR) official documents. The study has applied eclectic model of analysis (van Dijk's (1998) ideological Square, Wodak and Reisigl (2001-2009) *Discourse Historical Approach* (DHA) argumentative topoi, and Entman (1993) framing model) for with quantitative corpus analysis of Antconc software. The study reveals that USTR 2020 trade policies are framed, justified, and constructed in aligned with “America First” or “American Savior Archetype” and the ideologies of protectionism, national security, nationalism, authoritarianism and so forth. This study contributes to the economic political discourse studies by showing the role of ideologies in framing the trade discourse, besides the replicability of the theoretical and methodological triangulated model for the future studies.

Keywords: American Trade policy, Trump's Discourse, Ideological Representation, Critical Discourse Analysis, Corpus Analysis.

1. Introduction

U.S. Trade policy plays a pivotal role for regulating the domestic and global interests. With the disadvantages of trade liberalism, U.S. trade policy has taken a remarkable ideological dimension of protectionism and economic nationalism under Trump' administration (Baldwin and Eventt, 2020). Schoebaum (2023) addresses Trump trade policy “*America First*” with a defensive feature of unilateralism, paralysis of international institutions, and trade war. Therefore, Trump trade strategies affect the U.S. and the international economic stability. Vermehren (2021) explains that the official documents of USTR and the president’s annual reports are the central discourses to uncover the ideological representation and the convergent and divergent U.S. trade relations. Because of the complexity of trade policy context, the ideological dimensions are the key factors to understand trade discourse (Callaghan and O’Conner ,2019).

By reviewing the literature, limited studies have examined the priority of ideologies to frame the trade orientation, justification, and communication. Addressing this gap, the present study provides a critical discourse analysis approach to overcome the insufficient understanding for the role of ideological considerations in constructing Trump trade discourse.

2. Literature Review

Trade policy is the system to govern the trade relations among the states. The trade regulations include domestic laws and international agreements. Therefore, trade policy results from a set of interdisciplinary perspectives (van Grastek, 2008). Samer (2003) explains the issues that regulate within trade policy as in foreign transportation, travel, tourism, banking, and other international communication concerning business. There are two types of policies across the trade: trade protectionism and trade liberalism, the extremist version of protectionist policy appeared in the era of industrial revolution to protect small industries against the foreign trade (Kaempfer et al. 2002). On the other side, other countries use the protectionism to defense the national security by protecting the national industries and interests. Protectionism involves the restricted policies of tariffs and non- tariffs measures (Abboushi, 2016).

After World War II, trade liberation was addressed as a reaction against the capital power by liberal movements. As oppose to protectionism, trade liberalism provides some sort of relaxation among trade relations (Faribouz, 2006). The adaptation of free trade policies in trade liberalism reduces

trade barriers and enhances the economic growth and openness. Besides, the trade liberalism promotes the role of international institutions to regulate the challenges free trade (Liddle,2001).

American trade policy witnessed the trade policy protectionism from 1765 in order to establish the independence from British. Later protectionism appeared to defend the national interests. In 1940s, liberal multilateral relations were expanded to stabilize the relations with other countries (Baldwin, 1989). Trade liberalization has developed under different free trade agreements like *General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade* (GATT) in 1949 and *North America Free Trade Agreement* (NAFTA) in 1994 (Goldstein, 2004). During the economic crisis in 2008, trade liberalism was amended by some sort of protectionist policies to face the non- market access and unfair practices. In 2017, Trump trade slogan “America First” reinstated the extremist version of protectionism (Ligustro, 2020, p.2). Trump administration added more tariffs against North American trade relations, leaving the Transpacific Partnership (TPP) and declaring the trade war with China. Furthermore, Trump froze the role of *World Trade Organization* (WTO), describing its system with outdated and inconsistent (William, 2018). Under “America First” policy, the North America Free Trade Agreement replaced with *United State Mexico- Canada Agreement* (USMCA) (van Grastek, 2019). Trump trade policy embedded a set of ideologies that framed the trade policy, legitimated and constructed its strategies. Thus, it is necessary to scrutinize the linguistic construction with a sufficient approach. *Critical Discourse Analysis* (CDA) involves comprehensive framework to uncover ideological representation in trade policies.

CDA constructs from various linguistic theories and disciplines to critically evaluate certain issues in psychology, social practices, and anthropology. CDA uses the language as a social aspect to show different power relations, inequality, ideological representation of specific discourse (Blommaert, et al.2000). Because of CDA positive consequences of social reform and social change, many discourses can be handled as in political, economic, media, gender, institutional, educational, and cultural (Alvarez, 2002). The most prominent approaches in CDA are the socio-cultural approach for Fairclough, van Dijk's socio- cognitive approach, and Wodak et al. in *Discourse Historical Approach* (DHA).

In Fairclough's three- dimensional framework, discourse is addressed as social practice in three levels of intertextual analysis: describing the textual characteristics, interpreting the text in

discursive interactions, and explaining the text in socio-cultural dimension (Golbasi, 2017). van Dijk's socio-cognitive approach is concerned about the social cognition within local and global institutions, groups, and firms. van Dijk (2005) provides three levels in socio-cognitive analysis: the social level of relations and structures, the cognitive level for social and personal cognitions, and the discursal level. Furthermore, van Dijk (2000) adds the ideologies that control the social mind in specific group, explicitly or implicitly shape the discursal aspects by emphasizing positive WE versus negative THEM representation, and de-emphasizing positivity THEM and negativity WE. Zannini (2021) indicates that ideologies have existential position in trade policy to enforce hegemony and dominance and clarifying the power relations. By the collective efforts for Wodak and her colleagues, DHA is developed with multiple methods, theories, and discourses to identify ideologies across unequal power relations by legitimizing/ delegitimizing the social (institutional) practices with historical considerations (El-Naga, 2019). In argumentation topoi, the claim can be legitimated by connecting the argument with conclusion based on conditional structure and conclusion rules. Various topoi can be provided depending on the purpose and the occasions (Zagar, 2010). Within DHA, trade policy can be examined for a given time or continuity of historical trade aspect. For complementary approach, framing model enhanced the understanding of individuals and groups by present meaningful message. Therefore, the framing comprehends social, political, and cultural representations of decision makers. Entman (1993) framing model uses four tools of diagnosing: the problem, cause of the problem, moral evaluation, and remedies. Maxwell (2005) clarifies the data in trade policy describe the problem in informative and regulative provisions. In addition, the evaluations are provided by multi methods in order to enhance the validity and reliability.

In sum, CDA is appropriate to investigate the language of trade policy, CDA can explore the ideological representation across different disciplines. Ramos (2019) describes trade policy as a system with chain genres of government and secretariate reports and other institutions. Representation as an aspect identifies the inclusiveness and exclusiveness by the linguistic tools (framing marks) to reflect the ideologies under historical, economical, and political circumstances of trade discourse (Mengibar, 2015). Apparently, framing trade policy includes multiple sources of knowledge to understand the trade construction and to justify alternative policies.

Among the previous studies that conduct CDA studies in American political discourse, the limitations can be addressed for one reason or another. Arpzell (2020) provides the hidden power in his study “A Strategic Move toward Power” for president Trump concerning the trade discourse toward China. Arpzell's study adopts the CDA approach with theoretical framework for Fairclough three dialectal levels. His study concluded that the U.S. -China trade war resulting from unequal power between them. Mohammed (2020) in his study “Critical Discourse Analysis: Examining Donald Trump' s Political Speech” uses CDA approach to uncover Trump's ideologies during his speech. By using Halliday's Systematic Functional Grammer, Mohammed (2020) shows that Trump's speech shares the tactical strategies of US vs THEM by using modality, transitivity, and coherence. Another study for Awawdeh (2021), her study “A Critical Discourse Analysis of President Donald Trump's Speeches during Corona Virus Pandemic Crisis” investigates Trump's ideologies by using Fairclough (1995) three- dimensional model. Her study ended that Trump's grammatical structure and using comparative and superlative forms reflect his egoism and exaggeration. Pu (2023) conducts mixed method design to examine Trump's ideology toward China in his study “A Corpus- Based Critical Discourse Analysis of Trump's China – Related Political Discourse”. Pu (2023) applies the theoretical framework of Purvis and Hunt in CDA on his self – built corpus. finally, Pu (2023) determined that isolationism is the American ideology to confront China.

While such studies are undoubtedly important, the main problem is that little attention was paid to the role of ideologies to frame American Trade policy during Trump. In addition, much of these studies were concentrated on single theoretical framework and methodological base and widely adopted speeches as data analysis. Addressing these limitations, the present study adopts CDA approach to uncover the main ideologies that frame American Trade policy in Trump's Discourse using an eclectic model for analysis and triangulated methodology of corpus assisted tools for justifying the qualitative results.

3.Methodology

The present study describes the ideological representation that frame the American trade policy in Trump's (2017-2020) discourse. This section addresses the research design, data collection, data selection, and the analytical tools. The study adopts the explanatory sequential mixed- methods design to interpret the ideological framing, argumentation, and constructions.

3.1 Research Design

For deep understanding to the role of interaction between agencies, social structure, and causal reality in complex discourse (trade discourse), this study employs Critical Realism (CR) as a theoretical foundation that first indicated by Bhasher (1975). Newman (2020) clarifies that Critical Realism provides practical explanations between the “discursive and non -discursive” issues and clarity of the findings for CDA studies by analyzing the relation between social structure and social practice (p.6). In a line with CR's methodological perspective, the study adopts instrumental case study in explanatory sequential mixed methods design.

Figure 3.1: *Instrumental Case Study within Explanatory Sequential Mixed- Methods Design*

The data have collected from the official website of United States Trade Representative (USTR) “ustr.gov” for the Donald Trump Administration (2020). For corpus analysis in Antconc software, the data are converted in plain text (txt.) for uploading into Antconc.

Table 3.1

Size for Sub-Corpus: Toeken and Type Counts

Sub- Corpus	Token- Count	Type- Count
USTR (2020)	130070	7930

Based on the corpus results, extracts for prominent themes are chosen in purposive sampling to conduct the qualitatyive analysis. These extract are analyzed by the eclectic model to uncover the main ideologies that frame, justify and interprest in American trade policy (2020).

Table 3.2

Qualitative Corpus Patterns

Themes	Trump Discourse (2020)	
	Source	Purpose
USMCA	USTR p. 6	America First
Tariff enforcement	USTR p. 67	Defensive Tool
China	President's policy p.5	Trade enemy
WTO	USTR p.14	Exclusivism
U.S. IP Rights	USTR p.126	National Security

3.2 Criteria of Policy Analysis

The main criteria for policy analysis are specified by Wang and Soergel (1998) by systematic review of qualitative interpretation and quantitative analysis to fulfill the credibility and the validity of the study. Reliability and validity are the protocol for policy document analysis. For the credibility and validity of the present study, an eclectic model of analysis is guided by the corpus quantitative analysis. Ahmed (2025) explain that data saturation can ensure the credibility and validity of the research with no additional new issues appearing in the data. Therefore, the data saturation in this study are refined by analyzing 5 extracts after the verification of corpus analysis with no further issues to provide as ideological representation. For Ozkan (2024), the credibility can be confirmed by the authenticity, representativeness, and the clarity of the data from errors and exploitation. In current study, the authenticity of data is affirmed with its source as an official and public website of United States Trade Representative. Representativeness and clarity are validated by purposive choosing for relevant matters concerning local and international affairs in American Trade policy with equal sample size.

Ethical considerations for Creswell (2018) should be regarded in all stages in the research from the starting points, the stage of collecting the data, analyzing it, and reporting the results. In existing study, the authenticity ensures the ethical considerations by the open- access for the data as an official documents in public website. With transparent aim, research problem, and multiple phases of analysis, the study avoids any bias and subjective interpretation.

3.3 Analytical framework

The study has adopted the corpus assisted with CDA to provide explanation about the ideological representation of American trade policy in Trump discourse. For multiple evidences and meaningful results, different perspectives are regarded by the triangulation for theoretical framework and methodological investigators. In theoretical triangulation, the study applies three levels of analysis: the socio- cognitive approach for van Dijk (1998) ideological square, socio- historical approach and DHA argumentative topoi for Wodak and Reisigl (2001- 2009), and complementary approach for Entman (1993) framing theory.

Figure 3.2: Model of analysis

4. Analysis and Discussion

Under this section, the starting point of analysis is the corpus analysis to examine the most frequent themes, collocations, and clusters in the sub- corpus. Table 4.1 presents themes, the left-right collocations, and clusters in the sub- corpus with the frequencies.

Table 4.1

Frequent Themes with their Collocations and clusters

Word	Cluster	Collocation	Frequency
USMCA	Rebalances, modernizes, encourages implementing, benefiting	Suspension of tariff benefits, imposition of other penalties	117
Tariff	measures, commitments, bindings,	Rate, act, barriers, lines, determinations, agreements	184
China	denied, breaches, decreased, challenges, China and United States,	additional tariffs, disputes, unfair trade, export restrictions, panel request, non-market access, phase one agreement, section 301	521
WTO	Rules, reform, dispute system, obligations, failure, settlements	Appellate Body, overreached, inconsistent, and inadequate rules	755
US IP rights	Protection, enforcement, issues, piracy and counterfeiting, TRIPS, section 301, OCR	Bilateral, multilateral engagements, IP criminal actions, minimum standards in IP, IP progress	56

Depending on the results of corpus analysis, a more complete picture is provided by the qualitative analysis for the dominant themes. The qualitative examination of the extracts for each theme in the sub-corpus led to the identification of the dominant ideologies in trade policy constructions.

Extract 1

The enactment of the USMCA is the fulfillment of President Trump's promise to replace the outdated North American Free Trade Agreement (NAFTA) with a 21st century agreement that will lead to fairer trade and robust economic growth in North America. Negotiated over the course of two years, the USMCA exemplifies the President's vision for an America First trade policy. The USMCA will create more manufacturing jobs, defend America's competitive advantage in technology and innovation, protect workers and the environment, and secure greater market access for America's businesses, farmers and ranchers. The USMCA resulted from more than two years of hard work by the Administration, first in negotiations with Canada and Mexico, and then in lengthy consultations and negotiations with the United States Congress. The resulting agreement is a model for future United States trade agreements. (USTR, 2020, p.6)

This extract is produced by the United States Trade Representative (USTR) in the United States-Mexico- Canada (USMCA) agreement that applied in 2020 to replace North American Free Trade Agreement (NAFTA) during Trump presidency. The USMCA represents the renegotiating of NAFTA with different framework to ensure balance trade policy.

In van Dijk (1998) polarization, USMCA has the positive impact to replace the negative agreement NAFTA. With no emphasizing for bad effects for USMCA, NAFTA is addressed with imbalance trade practice toward U.S. economic interests. Therefore, NAFTA constitutes danger for American interests and USMCA is the resolution to protect the national economy "America First". With argumentative topoi (Wodak & Reisigl (2001), Trump administration justifies USMCA under a set of topoi. Topoi of threat, burden and history show NAFTA as threat and outdated agreement by the harmful past trade access. In the opposite side, USMCA operates many advantages in the manufacturing, defense, protection for domestic interests (topoi of advantage) and two years of hard-work (topos of number). USMCA is the fulfillment of president's promise (topos of authority) as modernized and 21st agreement (modernization topos). Within Entman (1993) framing model, the problem is framed under NAFTA and the causes of problem are identified with the bad policies of trade partners under this agreement. The bad evaluations for NAFTA are described by

imbalanced, unfair, outdated, as oppose to USMCA as modernized and 21st agreement. Thus, the remedy is defined with protective agreement USMCA.

In sum, the USMCA extract reflects the ideology of protectionism, authoritarianism, and economic nationalism under Trump's trade policy “America First”. These ideologies can be identified from the qualitative results by the eclectic model. By van Dijk ideological square, USMCA is represented by positive “WE” and NAFTA as negative “THEM”. The USMCA is justified argumentatively by topoi of Wodak and Reisigl's DHA. Positive topoi are diagnosed with USMCA as topoi of history, number, authority, advantage, and modernization. Other topoi (threat, burden, history) are hired to describe unfair, outdated, and inefficient NAFTA. According to Framing model (Entman, 1993), NAFTA is defined as problem and the cause of the problem the bad trade policies and practices for the trade partners. NAFTA is morally evaluated as outdated, unfair, and harmful trade agreement. To ensure American strength leadership, USMCA is the remedy that aligns with Trump's protective policy “America First”.

Extract 2

On July 16, 2018, the United States requested consultations with the European Union (EU) with respect to its imposition of additional duties on certain products originating in the United States. The EU imposed the additional duties in retaliation for the action the President took under Section 232 of the Trade Expansion Act of 1962, as amended, on imports of steel and aluminum products that threaten to impair U.S. national security. The U.S. consultations request alleges that the additional duties contravene the EU's obligations under the WTO Agreement because they: (1) fail to extend to U.S. products an advantage, favor, privilege or immunity granted by the EU to products originating in the territory of other WTO Members; (2) accord less favorable treatment to products originating in the United States; and (3) impose duties in excess of those set forth in the EU's schedule. (USTR, 2020, P.67)

This extract is constituted by USTR during Trump administration 2020 concerning the tariff enforcement toward EU under section 232 in the issues of steel and aluminum. The EU policies and practices are evaluated by retaliated and contravene. This extract provides an important context to comprehend the trade struggle between EU and U.S. under Trump trade policy.

Applying van Dijk model, the positive U.S. action addresses by the defensive tariff enforcement (economic nationalism) against EU negative policies toward steel and aluminum as U.S. national industries. With no objections to the U.S. additional tariffs to defend the national security (protectionism), the EU policies are badly violated the WTO obligations. The tariff justifications analyze under argumentative rules of DHA for Wodak & reisigl (2001). Topos of authority is identified by the tariff imposition under section 232 (authoritarianism). Addressing the EU bad policies before 2018, the topos of history justifies the U.S. tariffs imposition. Topos of burden, threat, and number are used by numerating three EU harmful policies and practices. By tariff enforcement under section 232, the U.S. steel and aluminum industries have the advantages, favor, and privilege (topos of advantage). The U.S. consultations and negotiations are the modernized policies to handle the EU dispute settlements (modernization topos). In Entman framing model, the EU policies are constructed as problem. The cause of the problem is the retaliated tariff as a reaction to tariff under section 232. For moral evaluation, EU policies are threatening, impaired the U.S. interests, and retaliated. The U.S. remedies are identified by consultations and negotiations with EU.

Consequently, the U.S. tariff imposition reflects the ideologies of protectionism, economic nationalism, and authoritarianism. U.S. Tariffs are the defensive tools to confront any unfair and harmful policies and practices for alliances or non-alliances under “America First”.

Extract 3

The President Entered into a Historic Phase One Agreement with China that Combats Unfair Trade Policies and Practices and Rebalances the U.S.- China Trade Relationship. When President Trump assumed office, the United States had suffered from China’s unfair trade policies and practices for decades. These unfair policies and practices harmed U.S. economic interests and undermined American manufacturing, services, and innovation. The Administration took specific action to combat certain of China’s unfair practices by initiating an investigation of China under Section 301 of the Trade Act of 1974...USTR bases exclusion determinations on an assessment of the extent to which the product implicated China’s “Made in China 2025” program, was not readily available in the United States or outside of China ...the Phase One Agreement expands trade, with enforceable

commitments by China to increase purchases of U.S. exports by no less than \$200 billion over the next two years in four major areas: manufactured goods, agriculture, energy, and services. (The President's 2020 Trade Policy Agenda, p.5)

The context in this extract is situated during Trump's presidency to confront China unfair trade access in the sectors of manufactured good, agriculture, intellectual property rights and so forth. The U.S. policies are operated under section 301 and bilateral phase one agreement to resolve U.S.- China disputes.

In van Dijk's ideological square, U.S. policies are addressed with positive “WE” for the resolutions under section 301 and phase one agreement to protect U.S. economic interests (authoritarianism, protectionism, and conservatism,). In contrary, China is the negative “THEM” in the polarization by the unfair and harmful policies and practices. With No local or international objections for U.S. policies toward China, China has no positivity to regard under the policies of “made in China 2025”. The U.S. confrontational policies are rationalized under certain topoi and argumentative rules (Wodak and Reisigl, 2001: DHA). Topos of authority can be addressed within the policies under section 301, and phase one agreement by bilateral conformity (authoritarianism). China trade program “made in China 2025” are described as unfair and imbalance, and harmful for U.S. economic nationality for decades (exclusivism under topoi of threat, burden and history). Topoi of number and advantage justify the U.S. policies with the number of advantages to rebalance and extend the U.S. exports with historic resolutions. Topos of modernization rationalizes phase one agreement as a bilateral negotiation in trade relations and essential cooperation. Framing model (Entman, 1993) constructs China discourse with the problem of China trade policies and practices for decades. The cause of the problem is the imbalance trade access toward U.S. national economy. China policies are evaluated by unfair, harmed U.S. national interests. The historic remedy is phase one agreement in aligned with “America First” policy.

In brief, the U.S. ideologies toward China unfair trade practices are constructed by trade protectionism and authoritarianism under section 232, conservatism and exclusivism with phase one agreement. U.S. trade policies are justified by argumentative rules with the ideology of economic nationalism to confront China trade discriminatory access.

Extract 4

During 2018 and 2019, the United States provided a series of extensive critiques objecting to the Appellate Body's disregard for the rules as set by WTO Members, and its attempts to alter rights and obligations under the WTO Agreement. Issues addressed included the Appellate Body's disregard for the mandatory 90-day deadline for appeals, unauthorized review of panel factual findings (including on domestic law), issuance of advisory opinions on issues not necessary to resolve a dispute, treatment of prior Appellate Body reports as precedent, and unapproved extension of Appellate Body members' service beyond established terms. These problems are not just procedural, but extend to matters of substance as well... Such overreach restricts the ability of the United States to regulate in the public interest and protect U.S. workers and businesses against unfair trading practices. USTR recently issued an extensive report that details the systemic problems with the WTO Appellate Body and dispute settlement process and addresses the correct approach to all of the issues identified... The United States has been working with the European Union and Japan to address these challenges (USTR 2020, p.14)

Under USTR 2020 report, this extract is established to present WTO inefficient system and its litigating entity to confront non-market access and unfair trade practices. U.S. descriptions for WTO outdated system and its Appellate Body overreaching are produced to justify U.S. ideological shift by unilateral trade decisions and calling for WTO reform.

By qualitative analysis, van Dijk's positive polarization addresses USTR reports about WTO Appellate Body to understand the global real situation. For negative polarization, WTO system and its Appellate Body are specified with substantial and procedural abuses. The U.S. resolutions toward unfair and non-market access are applied with no objections. WTO has no positive reaction to reform its system or its litigating entity practices. To justify the USTR policies, the argumentative topoi provide the rationale for these policies. Topoi of authority summit the authoritarianism under section 301 to face any unfair foreign practices. Topoi of history, number, threat, and burden are used to reflect WTO and its Appellate failure. Topoi of modernization and advantage are represented by U.S. efforts with EU and Japan to reform WTO system and ensuring U.S. leadership. With Entman's framing model, USTR provides WTO and its Appellate Body with substance and procedural problem. The causes of the problem are the WTO system and its litigating Body failure to handle non-market Access or to Settle the disputes legally and efficiently.

Appellate Body practices are evaluated as disregard the WTO rules, unapproved resolutions, unfair, and overreached. Remedially, U.S. cooperates with EU and Japan to provide correct approach to reform WTO challenges and protect U.S. national economy.

In short, U.S. anti- international institutionalism, exclusivism, conservatism, authoritarianism, and economic nationalism for WTO and dispute settlement Body can be observed in USTR agenda during the binary opposition, argumentative topoi, and framing trade policies construction. WTO system and Body settlement are addressed with negative polarization, topoi of burden, threat, number and history for systematic violations. In addition, WTO and its referred Body are constituted as international problem under framing model.

Extract 5

One of the top trade priorities for the Trump Administration is to use all possible sources of leverage to encourage other countries to open their markets to U.S. exports of goods and services and to provide adequate and effective protection and enforcement of U.S. intellectual property (IP) rights...Challenges include copyright piracy, which threatens U.S. exports in media and other creative content. U.S. innovators, including pharmaceutical manufacturers, face unbalanced patent systems and other unfair market access barriers. Counterfeit products undermine U.S. trademark rights and can also pose serious threats to consumer health and safety. According to the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), data on customs seizures indicates that the country whose goods are most counterfeited and pirated is the United States (almost 20 percent of total seizures around the world are of pirated and counterfeit goods whose right holders originate in the United States). Inappropriate protection of geographical indications, including the lack of transparency and due process in some systems, limits the scope of trademarks and other IP rights held by U.S. producers and imposes barriers on market access for U.S.-made goods and services... In addition, the theft of trade secrets, often among a company's core business assets and key to a company's competitiveness, hurts U.S. businesses, including small- and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). The reach of trade secret theft into critical commercial and defense technologies poses threats to U.S. national security interests as well. USTR deploys a wide range of bilateral and multilateral trade tools to promote strong IP laws and

effective enforcement worldwide, reflecting the importance of IP and innovation to the future growth of the U.S. economy. USTR seeks strong protection and enforcement for IP rights during the negotiation, implementation, and monitoring of IP provisions of trade agreements. (USTR 2020, p126)

For contextualizing this extract, USTR 2020 frames US IP rights with intensive impact on U.S. domestic interests. U.S. IP rights faced many unfair practices as in piracy and counterfeiting because of policies under past administrations and inefficient measures at the international level. The extract presents the USTR 2020 efforts to protect U.S. national IP rights during the trade agreements.

For polarization, U.S. negotiations, implementations and guidance for IP regulations are observed with positive “WE” actions. Unfair and imbalanced IP practices from trade partners and non-trade partners are described as negative “THEM”. Other negative and ineffective roles are designated for domestic and international measures to face IP piracy and counterfeiting. With no rejections for U.S. IP protection policies, the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) report confirms USTR report concerning U.S. IP violations. No positive efforts from “THEM” are devoted to resolve or stop their manipulated practices. The justifications are appeared under argumentative topoi of DHA (Wodak and Reisigl, 2001). Topos of authority provides the right for Trump administration to use section 301 and other sections related to protect national economy from unfair foreign practices (authoritarianism). Unfair practices are confirmed by topoi of number (20%), history (systematic violation), burden (counterfeiting, piracy, and theft), and threat (inappropriate protection, lack of transparency). Topoi of advantage and modernization reinforce the U.S. IP resolutions (renegotiations, implementations, and monitoring) trade agreements for innovation and IP growth. In framing model (Entman, 1993), the problem with IP rights is the negative practices of counterfeiting, piracy, and theft addressing internationally by OECD. The cause of the problem is the inappropriate and lack of clarity in the protection policies. Negative policies and practice are judged with imbalanced, unfair, threatened, and uncompetitive. Different trade agreements are the modernized remedy to ensure the application of “America First”.

A long with previous extracts, economic nationalism, authoritarianism are reflected in the U.S. resolutions to face IP violations. Protectionism and conservatism appear in trade agreements ensuring U.S. IP growth. USTR frames the IP situation under argumentative topoi in a way that justifies the U.S. confrontational policies. Trump's conservatism policy “America First” is framed under modernized and international remedies “trade agreements” to justify it.

5. Conclusion

USTR 2020 policies under Trump administration reflect the ideologies of protectionism, economic nationalism, conservatism, authoritarianism, exclusivism, individualism, and anti- international institutionalism. These ideologies are aligned with Trump's slogan “America First” in the issues concerning domestic and international affairs. Trump's trade policies concentrated on ideological shift in the themes of USMCA agreement, tariffs as confrontational tools, restricting China trade policies and practices, excluding WTO and its Appellate, and protecting U.S. IP rights. USTR 2020 provides a set of discursive strategies to justify (argumentative topoi) trade policies construction. For more comprehensive communication, USTR 2020 frames trade policies with four levels: problem definition, the cause of problem, the moral evaluation, and trade resolution. The present study offers future study in CDA analysis to compare USTR policies across different countries as in European countries to uncover the ideological differences and provide more comprehensive understanding about trade policy construction.

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